

WHICH NOMINATION COMMITTEE ATTRIBUTES MATTER IN IMPROVING FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE?

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Abstract

In this paper, we explore how a nomination committee of the board of directors of a firm influences the financial performance of the company. Recent articles have shown that nomination committee presence, size, independence, gender and meetings help to explain changes in the financial performance of a firm. Using data from Nigeria, covering 2008–2022 period, we verify that the previous literature overlooked the key role played by a group of variables denominated as nomination committee characteristics. Two variables (nomination committee presence and meetings) show to have roles in the decisions affecting firm financial performance. We also show that some control variables, such as firm size, firm listing age, and firm leverage, impact the financial performance of a firm. Finally, we show the bivariate relationship between nomination committee characteristics and firm financial performance. These findings are important to regulators, shareholders, boards, boards committees, auditors, managers, and scholars, since it opens space to further research. It also increases a body of knowledge in terms of the role of nomination committee in improving financial performance of a firm.

Keywords: Financial Performance, Nigeria, Nomination Committee Gender, Nomination Committee Independence, Nomination Committee Meetings, Nomination Committee Presence, Nomination Committee Size, Return on Asset

JEL Classification Codes: M21, M33, M48

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1. Introduction

The goal of a business is to increase stakeholder wealth (Gharaibeh & Qader 2017) through maximizing firm financial performance. The concept, firm financial performance, holds a great deal of weight in the business world. According to Abobakr (2017), a company's success is measured by its efficiency, its effectiveness, and the value it provides to its customers and investors. In addition, financial performance is used to gauge a company's success in achieving its goals. As a result, organizations need to consistently evaluate their performance and the elements that affect it. Performance, according to another definition, is all about how well a company uses its resources to achieve its goals (Handa, 2018).

Worldwide financial scandals and fraud have significantly impacted economies around the world and led to the failure of large firms (Al-Absy 2020, 2022a, 2022b). The financial crisis exposed serious flaws in firms' financial performance, as well as several problems including the manipulation of earnings and fraudulent business activities. Furthermore, the financial crisis revealed serious flaws in corporate governance processes, demonstrating the inability of financial reporting standards to provide sufficiently robust checks on company procedures.

Issues related to firm financial performance remain under scrutiny. According to Almaqtari et al. (2020), prior studies have raised serious concerns about financial performance. Investors, stakeholders, and policymakers all rank firm financial performance highly among their list of top concerns. Current and potential investors alike utilize assessments of firm financial performance to decide whether or not to maintain or acquire holdings (investments); as stated by Abobakr (2017), there is a need to know if the business is successful before committing any capital to it. According to agency theory, there is a conflict of interest between managers and shareholders, where managers are looking out for their own interests instead of maximizing those of shareholders.

Therefore, there was an immediate requirement for new and robust corporate governance procedures, which led to the formation of several committees, each responsible for a distinct function. Examples include the audit committee, the nomination committee (NC), the remuneration committee, and the risk committee. The majority of the available information points to poor corporate governance as a major cause of financial and business scandals (Garrett, 2020). Hence, firm financial performance may be enhanced using a variety of metrics, including corporate governance mechanisms, for example, nomination committee. The NC is a crucial part of the board of directors' committees that influences the company's operations. The functions of the NC can be summarized as board recruitment and succession planning, board evaluation, linking company strategy to recruitment, induction, training, and the development of new management (Chaudhry et al. 2020). So, the effectiveness of nomination committee is important.

Thus, independence of NC will enhance transparency in the process of director selection and enhances independence of the board as a whole and its decisions. The presence of independent directors on the NC will ensure highly qualified directors are selected and ensure enhanced monitoring of the management (Yeh et al., 2011). From agency theory perspective, the presence of independent nomination committee will ensure that quality directors are appointed to the board and board subcommittees (Chhaochharia & Grinstein, 2009).

Previous studies have extensively examined the relationship between corporate governance variables and firm performance (Osisioma et al., 2015; Udeh et al., 2017; Siyanbola et al., 2019). Despite the important role nomination committee plays and the impact of its attributes on firm financial performance, few studies have examined the impact of nomination committee attributes on firm financial performance especially in developing nation (Carcello et al., 2011). Most empirical studies investigated the relationship between corporate governance variables like board size, board meetings, board diversity, CEO duality, audit committee, remuneration committee, and risk committee and financial performance. However, the findings from these studies have been inconsistent and inconclusive. In the context of Nigeria, limited research has specifically examined the effect of nomination committee on financial performance. Existing studies in this area have mostly focused on the general impact of corporate governance variables on firm performance or have examined specific corporate governance proxies and their relationship with financial performance. Therefore, the current study at hand aims to fill this research gap and comprehensively impact of nomination committee attributes on firm performance.

The primary objective of this study at hand is to examine the impacts of nomination committee attributes on financial performance. The specific objectives of the study are as follows: to assess the effect of nomination committee presence on financial performance; to examine the effect of nomination committee size on financial performance; to investigate the effect of nomination committee independence on financial performance; to examine the effect of nomination committee gender on financial performance, and to examine the effect of nomination committee meetings on financial performance. Thus, the following hypotheses are formulated:

H₁: Nomination committee presence has no significant effect on financial performance.

H₂: Nomination committee size has no significant effect on financial performance.

H₃: Nomination committee independence has no significant effect on financial performance.

H₄: Nomination committee gender has no significant effect on financial performance.

H₅: Nomination committee meetings have no significant effect on financial performance

This paper contributes to the body of knowledge by providing an empirical study on the effect of the NC on the BOD's role in enhancing firm performance. The research applies two theories, agency and

resource dependence, which claim that an effective NC could improve the monitoring role of the BOD in enhancing the company's activities and operations and thereby boost firm performance. The study is considered very important for a country such as Nigeria in which, similar to other developing countries, many board directors are non-independent.

The study also help policymakers and regulators to evaluate the role of the NC, which currently seems to be ineffective and in need of improvement. It has been argued by several researchers, e.g., Mohammad et al. (2016) that the criteria for choosing directors need to be updated by authorities. Further, Al-Absy et al. (2018) stressed the importance of increasing the independence and efficacy of board committees, particularly the NC. The findings will also be helpful to the sector in general and the Nigeria context. Firms will be able to adapt as a result and profit accordingly. Future researchers will benefit from the study using the data and findings to their advantage.

2. Literature Review

Corporate governance encompasses the processes and mechanisms aimed at directing and controlling an organization's affairs in a manner that safeguards the interests of all stakeholders, while adhering to principles such as transparency, integrity, and accountability (Obeten et al., 2014). Corporate governance is now a topic with broad implications. As more businesses undergo significant alterations as a result of the confluence of technical advancement, sociopolitical shifts, and economic trends toward increasing globalization, corporate governance is a subject of growing relevance in developing countries (Al-Homaidi et al. 2019). The code of corporate governance in Nigeria states that the company must be headed by an effective, qualified, and expert board. In terms of the composition of the BOD, the minimum is five maximum number of directors is 15. The other requirements include that the chairman must be an independent director. Further, it indicates that the directors and senior officers must receive fair and reasonable compensation from the company. This is accomplished by creating a remuneration committee that contains three independent or non-executive directors (CBN 2018).

The nomination committee, which is one of the important committee of the board of directors, and the nomination committee it will help minimize agency conflict by ensuring that appointed board members work together to achieve shareholders interest. This means that the nomination committee plays an essential and important role in the success and failure of the company. The financial performance of companies collectively depends on whatever the nomination committee has appointed to the board and who is part of the executive management team. The nomination committee has to ensure that the right candidate with the right profile is selected to heighten the probability of success for the company (Appiah & Chizema, 2016). The analytical framework of this paper is shown in Figure 1. It illustrates the interaction with the dependent variable (firm financial performance) and the independent variables

(proxied with nomination committee presence, size, independence, gender and meetings). The analytical framework in Figure 1 lead to further articulation of the model specification in methodology section.

Figure 1. Analytical Framework

Source: Authors (2023)

The agency theory opines that the nomination committee be composed of majority independent outside directors with the right skill set and experience in strategic human resource planning in order that the board be provided with the multiplicity of the knowledge required to function well. Huse (2007) has suggested that in selecting directors to the nomination committee, the board must take into consideration how the candidate director cares about his or her reputation, since reputational concerns serve as trustworthy signals which the board can rely on. Directors' reputational concerns are as a result of past experiences which go a long way to influencing present and future actions and behaviours (Simoneti & Grogoric, 2004).

Firm financial performance is generally defined as a measure of the extent to which a firm uses its assets to run the business activities to generate revenues. It examines the overall financial health of a business over a given period and can be used to compare the performance of identical firms in similar industries or between industries in general (Atrill & McLaney, 2009). The main source of data for determining firm financial performance is the financial statement, the product of accounting which consists of the balance sheet which shows the assets, liabilities and equities of a business, the income statement that records the revenues, expenses and profits in a particular period, the cash flow statement which exhibits the sources and uses of cash in the period, and the statement of changes in the owners' equity that represents the changes in owner's wealth. Firm financial performance is commonly reflected in the calculation of financial ratios that show the link between numbers in the financial statement. The financial ratios may include the computation of the profitability, efficiency, liquidity, gearing, and investment of a particular firm.

According to Atrill and McLaney (2009), the ratios that may be utilized to calculate the firm's profitability are the return on assets (ROA), return on equity (ROE) and return on investments (ROI).

These ratios express the success of a firm in generating profits or returns from the resources owned. In contrast, the market-based measure is believed to be more objective because it relies on market responses to decision made by a firm.

Anderson and Biziak (2013) conduct a study examining the link between nomination committees (NC) and the financial performance of United Kingdom (UK) financial institutions. Their findings revealed a strong and statistically significant connection between a firm's NC and its Market Value (MV). Additionally, they observed a positive relationship between NC and the Return on Assets (ROA) of the firm, which serves as an indicator of financial performance. Their second objective focused on analyzing the impact of NC on UK financial firms during the 2007/2008 global financial crisis. The empirical evidence they gathered underscored that companies that implemented NC practices in their corporate boards experienced a positive and statistically significant effect on their ROA. Notably, they also identified an inverse relationship in terms of financial performance concerning the MV of these firms both before and after the global financial crisis.

Eminet and Guedri (2010) study delved into the influence of the existence and independence of nomination committees (NC) on the rewards and sanctions received by directors from the labor market, particularly for their roles as active monitors. This research was conducted using a sample of 200 publicly traded firms in France. The results from their study revealed that directors who were subsequently appointed to a nomination committee, especially when it was predominantly composed of independent directors and excluded the CEO, were significantly affected by their reputation as effective monitors of management. Therefore, the independence of the nomination committee was found to enhance transparency in the director selection process and bolster the overall independence of the board, as well as its decision-making capabilities.

Ramon (2001) examines 117 empirical research studies pertaining to audit committee (AC) composition, resources, and incentives, spanning from 2007 through 2015, revealed a global regulatory push to enhance the effectiveness of ACs with the aim of improving corporate governance quality. The author begins by providing a concise overview of the theoretical, normative, and empirical framework surrounding ACs, offering a comprehensive structure that encapsulates the latest advancements in empirical research within this domain. Subsequently, the text delves into the discussion of the AC monitoring process, which serves as a mechanism to elevate corporate governance quality. A prominent finding from these studies is the consistent positive impact of ACs' financial expertise on the quality of earnings. Within this context, the definition of AC financial expertise has become increasingly specific, with research assessing the beneficial effects of expertise in areas such as accounting, legal matters, or industry knowledge either individually or in combination. It's noteworthy, however, that both the quantity of research studies and the observed significance of results are notably lower for other aspects

of the monitoring process, including internal and external audit quality, as well as firm performance. Zona and Mimchilli (2013) investigate the primary objective, which was to explore the relationship between audit committees and the performance of Jordanian firms. Their research approach involved the use of OLS regression analysis to examine the connection between independent and dependent variables. The dataset encompassed 228 firms from both the industrial and services sectors. The study's findings revealed several key insights. First, there was a positive direction in the relationship between audit committee size and Return on Assets (ROA). However, this relationship was found to be statistically insignificant, meaning it did not reach a level of significance that would establish a strong correlation. Secondly, when considering audit committee size in relation to Earnings Per Share (EPS), the study found a positive direction in the relationship, and this relationship was also deemed statistically significant. In other words, there was evidence to suggest that a larger audit committee size had a meaningful impact on EPS. Lastly, the study's results indicated a statistically significant positive relationship between the number of audit committee meetings and ROA. This suggests that more frequent audit committee meetings were associated with improved Return on Assets.

In summary, the study's findings suggest that while there was a positive direction in the relationships between audit committee size, ROA, and EPS, the significance of these relationships varied. The connection between audit committee size and ROA was not statistically significant, whereas the relationship between audit committee size and EPS, as well as between the number of audit committee meetings and ROA, were statistically significant.

Kazemian et al. (2017) examine the interplay between Remuneration Committees (RCs), executive and board of director compensation, and firm performance within the Indonesian business landscape. Their investigation was based on a dataset encompassing 847 observations of firms listed on the Indonesian Stock Exchange (IDX) spanning the period from 2014 to 2017. One of the key findings of their research was a positive correlation between the presence of Remuneration Committees (RCs) and the compensation received by executives within these firms. This suggests that companies with established RCs tend to provide higher levels of compensation to their executives. Moreover, the study uncovered a significant positive relationship between the existence of RCs and firm performance. Specifically, higher levels of remuneration were associated with improved firm performance. Notably, this positive correlation was more pronounced in firms that had established a remuneration committee. Thus, the presence of an RC seemed to play a pivotal role in strengthening the connection between remuneration practices and corporate performance. The study's unique contribution lay in its exploration of these dynamics within an emerging market context, where the formation of RCs was voluntary rather than mandatory. This context-specific insight provides valuable perspective on the impact of RCs on compensation and performance in such environments. The implications of these findings extend to

regulators and company management not only in Indonesia but also in other emerging markets. The study suggests that encouraging or even mandating the establishment of RCs in emerging market settings could lead to more effective and performance-aligned remuneration packages. This, in turn, may contribute to improved corporate governance and overall firm performance.

In summary, Kazemian et al.'s research highlights the positive relationships between Remuneration Committees, executive and board compensation, and firm performance in Indonesia. It underscores the role of RCs in promoting effective compensation practices and their potential to enhance company performance, particularly in emerging markets where RC formation is voluntary. These findings carry significant implications for both regulatory bodies and corporate leaders in Indonesia and similar emerging market contexts.

Kaczmarek et al. (2012) examine the influence of NC on board diversity based on a sample of FTSE300 firms from 1999 to 2008 and reported that increasing the diversity of NC is likely to increase the diversity of board and that presence of CEO on the NC will have an influence on NC independence. The NC ensures that the board is composed in such a way that it will be able to perform its duties appropriately.

Jiraporn et al. (2009) conducted a comprehensive study focusing on the influence of Risk Management Committees (RMCs) on human capital within Australian listed firms during the period spanning from 2007 to 2013. The study's objectives included assessing the relationship between RMC human capital and firm performance, as well as examining its impact on the likelihood of bankruptcy. Drawing from human capital theory, this research investigated how specific attributes of RMC human capital, such as financial experience and tenure, influenced these critical aspects of firm performance and stability. To gather the necessary data, the researchers collected information from the annual reports of the subject companies. They employed regression analysis as their analytical tool to test their hypotheses. The results of their study underscored the significant role played by risk management human capital in enhancing firm performance and reducing the probability of bankruptcy. In particular, the findings highlighted that financial experience and tenure were the primary factors contributing to improved firm performance. Moreover, the study revealed an intriguing correlation regarding the gender composition of RMCs. Firms with female members on their RMCs exhibited a lower likelihood of bankruptcy compared to those without female representation. However, it's worth noting that the mere existence of an RMC, as well as the individual attributes of managerial experience, auditing experience, accounting experience, qualifications, and compensation, did not independently influence firm performance or the likelihood of bankruptcy. In conclusion, the study's results hold valuable insights for firms, shedding light on the costs and benefits associated with investing in RMC human capital. Additionally, the research provides valuable information to regulators concerning the state of RMC

human capital in Australia, offering implications for policymakers in terms of enhancing risk management practices related to firms' human capital.

Girangwa et al. (2020) investigate the impact of enterprise risk management on the performance of state corporations in Kenya. Grounded in agency theory, their research utilized an explanatory cross-sectional survey design. The primary data collection method involved structured questionnaires administered to 218 state corporations in Kenya. Subsequently, the gathered data underwent analysis through a combination of descriptive and inferential statistics. The hypotheses formulated for the study were assessed using multiple regression analysis. The outcomes of this investigation unveiled noteworthy findings. Specifically, the research revealed that various aspects of risk management, including risk structure, governance, and process practices, exerted a positive and statistically significant influence on organizational performance. One of the significant contributions of this study lies in its focus on advancing the empirical verification of agency theory in the context of enterprise risk management practices and their relationship with organizational performance. This empirical approach enriches the existing body of knowledge in this field. In light of these findings, the study provides a set of practical recommendations. It suggests that policymakers within state corporations should prioritize the integration of risk management practices across all functions and business units. This proactive approach can aid in addressing potential risks before they materialize, ultimately bolstering the overall performance of these organizations. In summary, Girangwa et al.'s research in 2020 offers valuable insights into the realm of enterprise risk management and its impact on the performance of state corporations in Kenya. By anchoring their study in agency theory and employing robust research methodologies, they contribute to both theoretical understanding and practical implications in the field of risk management and organizational performance improvement.

Chuirunesia and Bintara (2019) conduct a comprehensive investigation focusing on two primary aspects: (1) the roles and responsibilities of Risk Management Committees (RMCs) within non-financial Malaysian firms and (2) the correlation between RMCs and these firms' financial performance. The data utilized for this study were derived from corporate annual reports spanning the period from 2009 to 2016. The assessment of firms' financial performance was based on key indicators including Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), and Tobin's Q. To gauge the characteristics and effectiveness of RMCs, five proxy variables were employed: their size, degree of independence, the presence of key executives on the RMC, their level of knowledge and expertise, and the frequency of RMC meetings. The dataset was subjected to rigorous analysis using Panel Data Analysis in STATA 13. The research yielded valuable insights regarding the multifaceted roles assumed by RMCs within non-financial firms. These responsibilities ranged from fundamental tasks like reviewing and categorizing risks to more advanced functions such as approving risk strategies, presenting reports to the board of directors,

and furnishing assurance regarding the effectiveness of the risk management process. Significantly, the study unveiled a noteworthy association between the composition of RMCs and the financial performance of these firms. Specifically, the presence of key executives on the RMC, coupled with their knowledge and expertise, exhibited a positive correlation with firms' financial performance. In conclusion, Chuirunesia and Bintara's research underscores the voluntary nature of RMC establishment within non-financial firms, despite their significant impact. The study highlights that the formation of RMCs constitutes a pivotal strategy in the realm of corporate governance reform. By elucidating the diverse roles undertaken by RMCs and their tangible influence on financial performance, this research provides crucial insights that can inform corporate governance practices within non-financial firms.

Fali et al. (2020) conduct a comprehensive examination focused on assessing the impact of risk management committee (RMC) attributes, including its size, independence, and expertise, on the financial performance of listed insurance companies in Nigeria over the period spanning from 2012 to 2018. This study employed a sample of 24 insurance companies, drawn from a population of 27 firms. The researchers relied on secondary data extracted from the annual reports of these companies. The performance of these firms was evaluated using the Return on Assets (ROA) as the dependent variable. To analyze the data, the study utilized a Random Effect regression model. The study's findings revealed compelling evidence indicating that expertise within the risk management committee had a notable, albeit negative, impact on financial performance. However, the size and independence of the risk management committee were not found to exert any discernible influence on financial performance.

In summary, the research's primary conclusion underscores the potential constraints imposed by risk management committees on the propensity of management to undertake excessive risks, which, in turn, can lead to poorer financial performance within insurance firms. In light of these findings, the study provides a valuable recommendation: to enhance the effectiveness of risk management committees, insurance companies should consider expanding the composition of these committees by incorporating members with expertise in finance and actuarial sciences. This move towards greater expertise can contribute to more robust risk management practices and, ultimately, improved financial performance, Orjinta and Ikueze (2018) conduct a study aimed at investigating the influence of Audit Committee characteristics on the performance of a carefully selected group of non-financial firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Company Plc. Their research involved a sample of 50 listed firms, spanning the timeframe from 2007 to 2016. The study's findings were particularly noteworthy, as they unveiled a significant and positive correlation between two key Audit Committee characteristics—namely, Audit Committee independence and the frequency of Audit Committee meetings—and the performance of these firms. This relationship held true at a statistically significant level of 5%.

Nuhu et al. (2017) examine the effect of Audit Committees' Quality (Audit Committee members, Audit Committee meetings and Audit Committee financial expertise) on financial performance with a focus on the Nigerian food and beverages sector. The result of the study also shows an insignificant negative effect between Audit Committee members and financial performance of the Nigerian food and beverages sector.

Olayinka (2019) examines the effect of Audit Committee Effectiveness on the growth of Firms Performance in Nigeria with emphasis on Eight Public Quoted Banks in Nigeria. The findings revealed that Audit Committee size, frequency of Audit Committee's meetings and financial literacy of Audit Committee members have no significant effect on firms' performance in Nigeria. Furthermore, a study by Ruigrok et al. (2006) discover that companies with an NC are more likely to have more independent and international directors on their boards, but not more female board members. Furthermore, the existence of an NC is unrelated to board educational diversity but is linked to a higher level of nationality diversity.

3. Methodology

This section explains the techniques and approach employed in carrying out the empirical study on the effects of nomination committee characteristics on financial performance. To this end, the section starts with the research design, closely followed by the population of the study. This is followed by the sample size and sampling techniques, before we have a method of data collections which is closely followed by model specification and technique of data analysis. In this study, the research method adopted was an *ex post facto* type of research and content analysis technique. The study is longitudinal covering a period of fifteen (15) years. That is, from 2008 to 2022 using the 134 listed firms on the Main Board of the Nigerian Exchange.

The study uses secondary data (historical data) collected in respect of the variable captured, which were obtained from the financial statements and accounts of the sampled firms. Most previous studies have used annual financial statements. According to Gray et al. (1995), annual financial statements is the main official and legal document produced by companies on a regular basis and an important medium for their communications. Companies exercise control over the annual financial statements to prevent any possible journalistic information distortion or interpretation. Furthermore, according to Tilt (2001), financial statements are mandatory by legislation to be regularly produced particularly by all quoted corporate entities and by these facts making comparisons quite easy or simple.

Table 1 *Measurement of variables and expected signs*

Serial	Variables	Notation and Sources	A priori Sign
	Y1-Firm financial performance	Measured as profit after tax divided by total asset (%)	
1	X1: Nomination committee presence	Measured as 1 if there is nomination committee, or 0 otherwise in firm <i>i</i> in year <i>t</i>	+
2	X2: Nomination committee size	Measured as is the total directors and non-directors in the board nomination committee	-
3	X3: Nomination committee independence	Measured as the number of non-directors and non-executive directors in the nomination committee divided by nomination committee members size (%)	+
4	X4: Nomination committee gender	Measured as the number of female nomination committee members divided by nomination committee members size (%)	+
5	X5: Nomination committee meetings	Measured as number of meetings held by the board nomination committee members in a year	+
6	X6: Firm size	Natural logarithm of total asset	+/-
7	X7: Firm listing age	Measured as number of years a company is trading in the stock exchange	+/-
8	X8: Leverage	Measured as total liabilities divided by total asset	+/-

Source: *Authors' Compilation (2023)*

In this study, a model was specified to capture nomination committee characteristics and the extent of financial performance. Thus, the study adapted the model specified by Green and Homroy (2018), which was modified for the purpose of establishing the relationship between the dependent variable (financial performance) and the linear combinations of several independent (nomination committee presence, size, independence, gender, and meetings) and control (firm size, firm listing age, and leverage) variables captured in the study. The model reflects the identified nomination committee characteristics and the firm financial performance. The model was specified as:

$$FFP_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1NCP_{i,t} + \beta_2NCS_{i,t} + \beta_3NCI_{i,t} + \beta_4NCG_{i,t} + \beta_5NCM_{i,t} + \beta_6FS_{i,t} + \beta_7LAGE_{i,t} + \beta_8LEV_{i,t} + \epsilon_{i,t}$$

Whereas, FFP = Firm financial performance, NCP = Nomination committee presence, NCS = Nomination committee size, NCI = Nomination committee independence, NCG = Nomination committee gender, NCM = Nomination committee meetings, FS = Firm size, LAGE = Listing age, LEV = Leverage, β_0 = constant/intercept, β_{1-8} = Beta coefficients, *i* = Firm script (*i* = 134 firms), *t* = Time script (*t* = 15 years), ϵ = Error term.

Consequently, the Model examines the effects of nomination committee characteristics on firm financial performance. Thus, our *a priori* expectations are stated as follows:

$X_1 > 0$: Means that the presence of nomination committee generate a rise in firm financial performance.

$X_2 > 0$: An increase in nomination committee size leads to decrease in firm financial performance.

$X_3 > 0$: An increase in nomination committee independence leads to increase in firm financial performance.

$X_4 > 0$: A rise in nomination committee gender lead to increase in firm financial performance.

$X_5 > 0$: A rise in nomination committee meetings lead to increase in firm financial performance.

The econometric technique adopted in this study is the panel Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) regression technique. The rationale for its usage is based on the following justifications: the data collected have time and cross-sectional attributes that gives room for studying endogeneity within a firm and between firms; panel data regression provides better results since it increases sample size and reduces the problem of degree of freedom (Muhammad, 2012); it avoids the problem of multicollinearity and help to capture the individual cross-sectional (or firm-specific) effects that the various pools may exhibit with respect to the dependent variable in the model. Hausman and Taylor (1981) also recommended panel data estimation method because it enables a cross-sectional time series analysis which usually makes provision for a broader set of data points, but also because of its ability to control heterogeneity and endogeneity issues. Hence panel data estimation allows for the control of individual-specific effects usually unobservable which may be correlated with other explanatory variables included in the specification of the relationship between dependent and explanatory variables. Furthermore, the individual statistical significance test (T-test) and overall statistical significance test (F-test) are used. Importantly, the goodness of fit of the model is ascertained using the coefficient of determination (R^2). Our panel analysis is done after descriptive statistics and correlation analysis.

4. Results and Discussions

The descriptive statistics is in Table 2 for all the variables in the model.

Table 2 *Descriptive Statistics*

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
FFP	2010	1.379	2.881	-20.23	9.54
NCP	2010	.187	.39	0	1
NCS	2010	.701	1.533	0	9
NCI	2010	14.706	34.211	0	300
NCG	2010	2.171	9.802	0	75
NCM	2010	.374	1.013	0	6
FS	2010	8.964	.462	8.03	10.77
LAGE	2010	22.646	15.496	2	50
LEV	2010	86.863	18.875	8.63	254.75

Source: STATA 15.1

The descriptive statistics show that the mean of FFP is 1.379 percent, the mean of NCP is .187 percent, the mean of NCS is .701, the mean of NCI is 14.706 percent, the mean of NCG is 2.171. Furthermore, the mean of NCM is .374 times, the mean of FS is 8.964 times, the mean of LAGE is 25 years, and the mean of LEV is 86.963 percent. In the same vein, the standard deviation of FFP is 2.881 percent, the standard

deviation of NCP is .39 percent, the standard deviation of NCS is 1.533, the standard deviation of NCI is 34.211 percent, the standard deviation of NCG is 9.802. Furthermore, the standard deviation of NCM is 1.013 times, the standard deviation of FS is .462 times, the standard deviation of LAGE is 16 years, and the standard deviation of LEV is 18.875 percent. In the same vein, minimum mean of FFP is -20.23 percent, the minimum mean of NCP is 0 percent, the minimum mean of NCS is 0, the minimum mean of NCI is 0 percent, the minimum mean of NCG is 0. Furthermore, the minimum mean of NCM is 0 times, the minimum mean of FS is 8.03 times, the minimum mean of LAGE is 2 years, and the minimum mean of LEV is 8.63 percent. Finally, the maximum mean of FFP is 9.54 percent, the maximum mean of NCP is 1 percent, the maximum mean of NCS is 9 members, the maximum mean of NCI is 300 percent, the maximum mean of NCG is 75 percent. Furthermore, the maximum mean of NCM is 6 times, the maximum mean of FS is 10.77 times, the maximum mean of LAGE is 50 years, and the maximum mean of LEV is 254.75 percent.

A major fall out of the results in Table 2 is the spread in FFP, that is, the standard deviation (2.881) is larger than the mean (1.379), which suggests that firm financial performance actually deserves to be researched, because of its instability. The Pearson correlation coefficient matrix was used to identify the direction and strength of the relationship between the nomination committee characteristics and firm financial performance. Table 3 is a report of the results of correlation analysis.

Table 3 *Correlation Matrix*

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)
(1) FFP	1.000								
(2) NCP	0.008 (0.781)	1.000							
(3) NCS	0.024 (0.432)	0.955*	1.000						
(4) NCI	0.007 (0.819)	0.915*	0.869*	1.000					
(5) NCG	-0.010 (0.736)	0.470*	0.458*	0.518*	1.000				
(6) NCM	0.039 (0.206)	0.771*	0.785*	0.763*	0.378*	1.000			
(7) FS	0.163* (0.000)	0.037 (0.227)	0.030 (0.322)	0.054 (0.070)	0.055 (0.065)	0.061* (0.045)	1.000		
(8) LAGE	-0.130* (0.000)	-0.066* (0.030)	-0.090* (0.003)	-0.030 (0.313)	-0.055 (0.064)	-0.048 (0.116)	0.289* (0.000)	1.000	
(9) LEV	-0.343* (0.000)	-0.044 (0.150)	-0.049 (0.109)	-0.031 (0.300)	0.007 (0.821)	-0.031 (0.310)	-0.216* (0.000)	0.105* (0.000)	1.000

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Source: STATA 15.1

From the results in Table 3, the bivariate relationship between nomination committee presence and firm financial performance is positive but not significant. Similarly, the bivariate relationship between nomination committee size and firm financial performance is positive but not significant. Also, the

bivariate relationship between nomination committee independence and firm financial performance is positive but not significant.. However, the bivariate relationship between nomination committee gender and firm financial performance is negative, but not significant. The bivariate relationship between nomination committee meetings and firm financial performance is positive but not significant. In contrast, the bivariate relationship between firm size and firm financial performance is positive and significant. In sharp contrast, the bivariate relationship between firm listing age and firm financial performance is negative but significant. Finally, the bivariate relationship between leverage and firm financial performance is negative and significant.

The GMM regression results for the Model are given in Table 4.

Table 4 *GMM Regression results*

GMM estimation

Number of parameters = 9

Number of moments = 9

Initial weight matrix: Unadjusted

Number of obs = 2010

GMM weight matrix: Robust

FFP	Coefficients	Robust standard error	z	P> z	[95% Conf	Interval
NCP	-1.028035	.5643057	-1.82	0.068	-2.134054	.0779837
NCS	.153198	.1335788	1.15	0.251	-.1086117	.4150077
NCI	.0006502	.0039166	0.17	0.868	-.0070263	.0083266
NCG	-.0063964	.0059845	-1.07	0.285	-.0181258	.005333
NCM	.1733042	.0929476	1.86	0.062	-.0088698	.3554782
FS	.8222836	.2116752	3.88	0.000	.4074078	1.237159
LAGE	-.024861	.0054118	-4.59	0.000	-.0354679	-.0142541
LEV	-.045466	.0073141	-6.22	0.000	-.0598014	-.0311307
/b0	-1.455217	2.016891	-0.72	0.471	-5.408251	2.497816

Source: STATA 15.1

The coefficients of the nomination committee presence, meetings, firm size, firm listing age and leverage are statistically significant at the level 10 percent. The independent variables (NCP and NCM) affect the dependent variable in the same direction. According to the empirical results, as the nomination committee is created, the level of firm financial performance reduces; as the frequency of meetings increases, firm financial performance reduces. This result is consistent with our a priori expectation on nomination committee meetings. In respect to the control variables, the three variables are all significant. While firm size is positive and significant with firm financial performance, both listing age and leverage are negatively significant.

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

This research has collected relevant data of listed companies in Nigeria and analyzed to find out the impacts of NC on firm financial performance. From the detailed study about the NC variables, the study offers some suggestions to improve the firm financial performance. From this study, it is observed that the presence of nomination committee reduces firm financial performance. The main reason is that with the creation of new additional committee, comes with emoluments and allowances, which results in increase cost of operations. Therefore, the task of nomination committee may be handled by the board itself. In the case of nomination committee size, it is not a determinant of firm financial performance. Managers should not allow large nomination committee size. The same thing applies to the independence of the nomination committee. It is not significant at all, as far as firm financial performance is concerned. Similar findings are obtained in the case of gender of nomination committee. However, in the case of nomination committee meetings, the results are significant with firm financial performance. In the areas of recommendations, it should be noted that this study uses 134 of the 156 listed firms on the Nigerian Exchange; therefore, future research may increase the sample size. Furthermore, the data set is for 15 years (2008-2022), future research may decide to increase the number of observations, which in the instant case is 2,010. There are so many nomination committee characteristics, but this study considers only five variables (presence, size, independence, gender and meetings) further research may cover more variables. Firm financial performance was measured by return on asset, however, there are several ways to measure financial performance; future research may decide to use return on equity, return on investment, or return on capital employed.

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